

CHALLENGES AND RESILIENCE IN MODULAR LEARNING: A STUDY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL EDUCATORS' PREPAREDNESS AND COMMITMENT

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Challenges and Resilience in Modular Learning: A Study of Senior High School Educators' Preparedness and Commitment

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Abstract

In response to the global pandemic, the modular approach has become a widely adopted, cost-effective alternative learning method. This study examined the preparation, commitment, and resilience of Senior High School teachers and administrators in Consolacion, Cebu, and explored how these factors influenced their perceptions of modular learning. Findings indicate that both groups demonstrated high levels of commitment and resilience, with teachers attributing their resilience to a sense of duty as front-liners and strong support from stakeholders. Notably, differences in preparedness were observed: administrators' higher resource access did not predict teachers' preparedness, but teachers' preparation significantly correlated with their resilience. Key challenges included inconsistent support from home tutors and limited resources for module distribution. These results highlight the need for enhanced support systems to address barriers and sustain educators' commitment to modular learning.

Keywords: *development education, modular approach, teachers and administrators, descriptive-quantitative, Philippines*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly disrupted education worldwide, prompting many countries, including the Philippines, to implement alternative delivery modes to continue instruction while ensuring safety. The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines introduced distance learning options to avoid prolonged school closures. Among these alternatives, modular learning became a key approach, particularly in areas where internet connectivity is limited. Modular learning relies on self-learning modules (SLMs) based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs), enabling students to engage in self-paced learning despite physical separation from teachers (DepEd, 2020). This approach aims to maintain educational continuity under unprecedented constraints, presenting new demands on both students and educators.

In the context of modular learning, educators are expected to demonstrate preparation, commitment, and resilience. Preparation refers to their readiness and training for delivering content through SLMs, commitment denotes their dedication to supporting students' learning goals, and resilience highlights their capacity to adapt to the stress and uncertainty brought about by the pandemic. These concepts are crucial for understanding the challenges faced by educators who must balance module development, distribution, and monitoring of student progress while adapting to new teaching conditions.

Previous studies have explored the use of modular learning and the resilience of teachers, particularly in crisis contexts and within developing countries, as emergency alternatives to traditional in-person instruction. These studies generally underscore the value of modular learning in sustaining educational access during disruptions; however, they also point to several critical factors that impact its success. For instance, research by Talain & Rodas (2024) highlights that while modular learning offers a flexible approach to education in emergencies, its effectiveness is closely tied to the adaptability and resourcefulness of teachers who often bear the responsibility for content delivery, monitoring, and support.

In low-resource settings, teachers' resilience and commitment are frequently tested as they manage the increased workload associated with creating, distributing, and assessing modular content. Studies in countries with similar socioeconomic profiles to the Philippines have identified a range of challenges faced by educators in modular learning environments, including limited access to training, insufficient material support, and lack of institutional guidance. This has led to heightened occupational stress, as teachers must continuously adapt to these challenges while still aiming to meet educational objectives (Bozkurt et al., 2020). While this body of research highlights important challenges, it often lacks a detailed examination of how teachers' personal and professional attributes—such as their levels of preparation, commitment, and resilience—directly influence the effectiveness of modular learning implementation.

Moreover, specific studies focusing on the Philippines' educational context are limited, particularly regarding how educators in under-resourced settings navigate the demands of modular learning during the pandemic. While resilience and adaptability are increasingly recognized as crucial qualities for educators in crisis situations, there is still a gap in understanding how these factors interact with teachers' perceived effectiveness in delivering modular education. Existing literature has yet to fully address how teachers' readiness and ongoing commitment to modular education can mitigate or exacerbate the educational challenges posed by crises like COVID-19, especially in local, nuanced settings such as Cebu, where access to resources may vary.

In summary, this study investigates the preparedness, commitment, and resilience of Senior High School educators in Consolacion, Cebu, as they navigate the demands of modular learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. By examining these factors and their impact

on effective modular education delivery, this research aims to fill a crucial gap in understanding how educators' adaptability influences educational continuity in crisis contexts. The findings will contribute insights that may inform policies and support systems tailored to enhance educator resilience and instructional effectiveness in similar settings.

Research Questions

This research assessed the level of manifestation on preparedness, commitment, and resiliency in the delivery of modular and learning approach for Senior High School in the selected schools in the District of Consolacion, Cebu, during the school year 2020-2021. Specifically, this study answered to the following queries:

1. What is the profile of school administrators and teacher-respondents in terms of?
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5. plantilla position;
 - 1.6. years in service, and
 - 1.7. performance rating?
2. What is the level of manifestation of respondent groups in modular approach as to:
 - 2.1. preparedness;
 - 2.2. commitment;
 - 2.3. resiliency?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the school administrators' and teachers' level of preparedness and commitment?
4. Is there a significant relationship between teachers' level of preparedness and their extent of resiliency?
5. What are the challenges and barriers encountered by the teacher in the modular approach?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what latent modular approach supervision plan can be designed?

Literature Review

This literature review examines the concept of teacher preparedness in the context of modular instructional delivery in senior high school. The focus is on identifying key factors contributing to effective teaching in this evolving educational landscape, particularly in relation to teacher quality, subject matter expertise, pedagogical knowledge, and teacher resilience. This review aims to establish a theoretical foundation, highlight existing gaps in the literature, and define key concepts relevant to the research area.

Teacher Quality and Preparedness:

The concept of teacher quality is multifaceted and often debated. While there is no universally agreed-upon definition, several organizations have developed standards for teacher quality, including the Interstate New Teacher Assessment and Support Consortium (INTASC), the National Board for Professional Teaching Standards (NBPTS), and the National Council for Accreditation of Teacher Education (NCATE). These organizations emphasize the importance of subject matter knowledge, pedagogical skills, and the ability to connect curriculum to students' lives (Lewis et al., 2019).

Teacher Qualifications and Subject Matter Expertise:

Beyond Traditional Credentials. Recent research suggests that traditional measures of teacher qualifications, such as certification and degree level, may not fully capture the complexities of effective teaching (Ronfeldt, 2021).

The Role of Subject Matter Expertise. The importance of subject matter expertise remains a key focus. Gardner (2019) demonstrated a strong correlation between teachers' subject matter knowledge and student achievement, particularly in STEM fields. However, the study also highlighted the need for teachers to possess pedagogical skills to effectively translate their subject knowledge into engaging and effective instruction.

The Impact of Experience. The role of experience in teacher effectiveness is complex. Shanks et al., 2022 found that while experience can contribute to improved teaching practices, it is not a guarantee of effectiveness. The study emphasized the importance of ongoing professional development and mentorship for teachers at all stages of their careers.

Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Teacher Commitment:

Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK). The concept of PCK, originally proposed by Shulman in 1986, remains a cornerstone of effective teaching. Recent research continues to underscore its importance in the context of contemporary educational challenges. For example, Chai et al., (2019) found that teachers with strong PCK were better equipped to adapt their teaching to diverse learners and effectively implement new educational technologies. This finding highlights the dynamic nature of PCK, requiring teachers to continually update their knowledge and skills to meet evolving student needs.

Teacher Commitment. Teacher commitment, often described as a strong emotional attachment to the teaching profession, is a critical factor in teacher effectiveness and student success (Bardach et al., 2022). Recent research has explored the multifaceted nature of teacher commitment, identifying factors such as job satisfaction, sense of purpose, and belief in the value of education as key contributors to teacher dedication (Ostad et al., 2019).

The Interplay of PCK and Teacher Commitment. Research suggests that PCK and teacher commitment are interconnected. Teachers with strong PCK are more likely to be committed to their profession, as they find satisfaction in their ability to effectively teach and see their students learn. Conversely, committed teachers are more likely to invest in their professional development, seeking opportunities to enhance their PCK and improve their teaching practices (Wiener et al., 2018).

Teacher Resilience and Modular Instructional Delivery:

The concept of teacher resilience, defined as the ability to adapt and thrive in the face of adversity, has gained significant attention in recent years, particularly within the context of rapidly evolving educational landscapes. Modular instructional delivery, with its emphasis on flexibility, individualized learning, and technology integration, presents both opportunities and challenges for teachers. Resilience is increasingly recognized as a crucial factor in navigating these challenges and ensuring effective teaching and learning.

Recent Research on Teacher Resilience:

Resilience in the Face of Change: Beltman et al., (2018) found that teachers who exhibited high levels of resilience were better able to adapt to the demands of modular instruction, including the use of new technologies, the need for flexible lesson planning, and the increased focus on student-centered learning.

Resilience and Stress Management: Shay et al., (2021) highlighted the importance of resilience in helping teachers manage the stress associated with modular instructional delivery. The study identified strategies such as self-care, seeking support from colleagues, and engaging in professional development as key factors in promoting teacher resilience.

Resilience and Student Outcomes: Fernandes et al., (2019) demonstrated a positive correlation between teacher resilience and student achievement in modular learning environments. The study suggested that resilient teachers were better able to create a supportive and engaging learning environment, fostering student motivation and academic success.

The Importance of Fostering Teacher Resilience:

Recognizing the vital role of teacher resilience in the successful implementation of modular instructional delivery, educators and policymakers are increasingly focusing on strategies to promote and support teacher resilience. This includes providing professional development opportunities that focus on stress management, building positive relationships, and developing adaptive teaching practices. Creating a supportive school culture that values collaboration, innovation, and continuous learning is also crucial for fostering teacher resilience.

Gaps in the Literature:

While existing research acknowledges the importance of teacher quality, encompassing subject matter expertise, pedagogical knowledge, and commitment, a significant gap remains in the understanding of how these factors interact within the context of modular instructional delivery, particularly in senior high school settings.

Key Areas for Further Exploration:

The Interplay of Teacher Quality Factors: While individual components of teacher quality have been studied, there's a need to delve deeper into how these factors interact and influence each other within the dynamic environment of modular instruction. For example, how does strong subject matter expertise contribute to a teacher's ability to adapt their teaching to diverse learners within a modular framework? How does teacher commitment impact their willingness to embrace new technologies and innovative teaching strategies?

The Role of Teacher Resilience: Existing research often focuses on individual components of teacher quality, but the crucial role of teacher resilience in navigating the challenges of modular instruction deserves further investigation. How does resilience enable teachers to adapt to changing circumstances, manage student engagement, and maintain a positive attitude amidst the complexities of modular delivery?

Senior High School Specific Considerations: The unique needs and challenges of senior high school students, who are preparing for post-secondary education or careers, require a nuanced understanding of how modular instruction impacts their learning experiences. How does teacher resilience contribute to meeting the diverse needs of this student population within a modular framework? What specific strategies can be developed to support teachers in effectively implementing modular instruction in senior high school settings?

The Need for Actionable Insights:

Addressing these gaps in the literature is crucial for developing effective strategies to support teachers in successfully implementing modular instruction, particularly in senior high schools. Further research should aim to provide actionable insights that can inform teacher training programs, professional development opportunities, and school policies designed to foster teacher resilience and

enhance the effectiveness of modular teaching practices.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-quantitative research design with a differential approach. Data were collected from Senior High School administrators and teachers in the district of Consolacion using a structured survey form over a specified period. The independent variables in the study were the levels of preparedness, commitment, and resilience exhibited by these educators during the "new normal." The dependent variable was the respondents' perceptions of the effectiveness of modular instruction.

To analyze the data, Pearson's r correlation coefficient was applied to assess the relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Additionally, other relevant statistical tests, such as t-tests and ANOVA, were conducted to identify any significant differences based on demographic factors. The findings are presented in both tabular and narrative formats, providing a detailed quantitative representation and interpretation of educators' preparedness, commitment, and resilience in delivering modular instruction during the pandemic.

Respondents

The study involved 68 participants from six senior high schools located in Districts 1 and 2. The respondents included both administrators and teachers, with six administrators (one from each school) and 62 teachers participating. This distribution ensures data was collected from a diverse range of individuals within the targeted senior high school population, providing a representative sample for the study.

While the sample size of 68 participants may appear modest, it is appropriate given the study's specific focus on educators within a defined geographical area. This sample size was determined based on the total population of senior high school educators in the selected districts, aiming to capture a meaningful cross-section of perspectives. Future studies could expand the sample to enhance generalizability, but this sample size is considered sufficient for exploring key relationships and identifying trends within this population.

Instrument

The study utilized a modified questionnaire consisting of three parts: Respondent's Profile, Respondents' Perception towards the modular approach, and Challenges and Barriers to Modular Instructions. The questionnaire was adapted from DepEd Cebu Province Division Memorandum No. 590 s. 2019, focusing on coaching and mentoring for cooperating teachers.

The first part gathered personal information on respondents, including age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, position held, length of service, and performance rating. The second part assessed respondents' perspectives on preparedness, commitment, and resiliency towards module-based instruction through a set of questions evaluating their capabilities in lesson planning, material reproduction, and supporting struggling learners.

Scoring for perception on preparedness, commitment, and resiliency ranged from 1 to 5, reflecting the frequency of the behavior observed. The same scoring system was applied to administrators' perspectives on teachers' readiness for modular instruction.

Part 3 listed challenges and barriers to modular instruction, aligned with the DepEd memorandum. The questionnaire underwent a pre-testing phase with six senior high school teachers to ensure clarity and understanding. Subsequently, it was validated by the research adviser to eliminate errors, ensuring the reliability of the final instrument before administration to the actual respondents.

Procedure

The research procedure began with the researcher obtaining approval from key stakeholders, including the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisor, and school administrators, to conduct the study. Following the necessary approvals, the researcher distributed the questionnaires according to a predefined timeline. To enhance engagement and address the challenges of limited response rates during the questionnaire administration, the researcher opted for personal distribution, allowing for direct interaction with respondents. This approach not only facilitated immediate clarification of any questions but also helped establish rapport, encouraging greater participation. Despite these efforts, some respondents still exhibited limited engagement, which could have affected the comprehensiveness of the data collected. To mitigate this issue, the researcher provided clear instructions on the study's purpose and significance, ensured anonymity and confidentiality, and scheduled convenient times for respondents to complete the questionnaires.

Data collection was conducted over a two-week period in designated settings that promoted focus and confidentiality. The questionnaires consisted of three parts: demographic information, perceptions of modular instruction, and challenges encountered. The scoring system used to evaluate respondents' levels of preparedness, commitment, and resilience towards module-based instruction was structured on a scale from 1 to 5, with each score corresponding to specific verbal descriptors: 1 (Never), 2 (Rarely), 3 (Sometimes), 4 (Often), and 5 (Always). This scoring not only quantified respondents' perceptions but also provided insight into how frequently these

behaviors were exhibited, thus translating into meaningful insights about their preparedness, commitment, and resilience levels.

In terms of statistical treatment, the demographic characteristics of respondents, such as age, gender, length of service, educational attainment, position, and years in teaching or administration, were analyzed using simple frequency distribution and percentages. Additionally, Pearson's *r* correlation coefficient was employed to ascertain the relationships between the levels of preparedness and commitment of school administrators and teachers, as well as the correlation between teachers' preparedness and resilience levels. This statistical analysis aimed to uncover the dynamics between various variables within the context of modular instructional delivery, offering valuable insights into teacher perceptions and readiness for implementing modular teaching strategies.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher obtained written permission from the principal to conduct the study and collect qualitative data on school premises, ensuring adherence to institutional guidelines. Informed consent was then presented to all respondents, outlining the study's purpose, their rights, and the implications of participation. This process emphasized the protection of respondents' confidentiality and the safeguarding of their identities, ensuring that data was anonymized and stored securely.

To foster a comfortable environment, the researchers allotted sufficient time for respondents to complete the questionnaires. They provided guidance on the questions and how to answer the survey accurately, ensuring clarity and comprehension while respecting respondents' autonomy and encouraging honest responses.

After completing the questionnaires, the researcher promptly collected and tabulated the data, ensuring the secure handling of all information gathered. Throughout the study, the researcher maintained ethical standards by prioritizing participants' rights, confidentiality, and well-being, thus fostering a respectful and supportive research environment. This approach ensured that the study adhered to principles of beneficence, aiming to contribute to the improvement of educational practices, and non-maleficence, minimizing any potential risks to participants.

Results and Discussion

This section delves into the analysis and interpretation of data collected from selected Senior High Schools in Districts 1 and 2 of Consolacion, Cebu, within the Division of Cebu Province. The analysis explores the demographic profile of the respondents, assesses the level of preparedness, commitment, and resilience towards modular instruction among teachers and administrators, examines the relationships between these factors, and identifies the challenges and barriers encountered in implementing modular teaching strategies, providing a comprehensive understanding of the current state of modular instruction in these schools.

Profile of the Respondent Groups

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the respondents' backgrounds and experiences, a detailed profile was developed. This profile encompassed key demographic variables such as age, gender, civil status, highest educational attainment, plantilla position, years of service, and performance rating. This information provides valuable context for interpreting the respondents' perceptions and experiences related to modular instruction.

Age

Age refers to the number of years of the existence of the teacher respondents in the world as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. *Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Administrator</i>		<i>Teacher</i>		<i>Tota l</i>
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	
under 25	0	0	4	5.88	4
25-30	0	0	12	17.65	12
31-35	0	0	7	10.29	7
36-40	1	1.48	10	14.71	11
41-45	0	0	12	17.65	12
46-50	2	2.94	16	23.53	18
51-55	3	4.41	1	1.47	4
Total	6	8.82	62	91.18	68

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents are between 25-50 years old with the highest number of them belong to the 46-50 age category and the least number of respondents belonging to the 51-55 years old age category.

The youngest among respondents are below 25 years old comprising 5.88 percent of the total number while the oldest are 51-55 years old comprising 5.88 percent of the total number.

This implies that a majority of the respondents are in their prime years. They are energetic enough to do their tasks, duties and responsibilities. This is considered as the workaholic stage that leads to commitment. On the other hand, minority of them are close to the retirement.

Gender

Gender refers to male and female. Presented in Table 2 is the profile of the respondent groups in terms of their sexes.

Table 2. *Gender*

Gender	Administrator		Teacher		Total
	f	%	f	%	
Male	1	1.47	19	27.94	20
Female	5	7.35	43	63.24	48
Total	6	8.82	62	91.18	68

This Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents are female comprising 70.59 percent of the total number while 29.41 percent are male. It proves that female outnumbered male respondents. In comparison, based on Education Gender Statistics and Indicators, in the Department of Education, data revealed that there are 89.58% government school are female teachers and only 10.42% percent are male teachers. Results illustrate that 90 percent of this job are women and expected to possess gentle approach. It further implies that there are tasks suited to men are also assigned to women teachers like, for example, the Boy Scout of the Philippines which is part of the DepEd Special Programs. The technical subjects are also done by female teachers. Thus it is suggested that the school innovate the gender sensitivity programs for the teachers and pupils.

Civil Status

Civil Status deals with the marital status of the respondents. Illustrated in Table 4 are findings in terms of civil status.

Table 3. *Civil Status*

Civil Status	Administrators		Teachers	
	f	%	f	%
Married	5	83.30	36	58.06
Single	0	0.00	26	41.94
Widow	1	16.70	0	0.00
Total	6	100	62	100

Table 3 reveals that a majority of both administrator and teacher respondents are married, with 83.30% and 58.06% respectively falling into this category. While Peralta (2019) suggests that marital status can influence multitasking and instruction, drawing a direct correlation between marital status and preparedness for modular instruction is challenging. It's important to avoid making assumptions about individual capabilities based solely on marital status.

The study by Peralta (2019) highlights the potential impact of marital status on multitasking and instruction, but further research is needed to understand the specific implications for modular teaching. While married administrators and teachers may have experience with multitasking and managing student behavior, it's crucial to recognize that individual needs and skill levels vary greatly. Schools should provide training and seminars to equip all educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively implement modular instruction, regardless of their marital status.

Highest Educational Attainment

Highest educational attainment is the highest level in education that the respondents attained as of the present. Illustrated in Table 4 are the data regarding the respondents profile as to educational qualification.

Table 4. *Highest Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Administrator		Teachers	
	f	%	f	%
Bachelor's Degree	0	0	27	43.55
With Masters' Units	0	0	13	20.97
Master's Degree	6	100	15	24.19
With Doctorate Units	0	0	0	0
Doctorate degree	0	0	7	11.29
Total	6	100	62	100

Table 4 reveals that a significant portion of respondents (43%) did not pursue graduate studies, while 45.16% completed academic units or obtained a Master's degree. Notably, a higher percentage of respondents (24.19%) have completed a Master's degree program compared to those who have taken units towards a Master's degree (20.97%). This suggests that a substantial proportion of respondents value advanced education and have chosen to fully complete a Master's degree program.

The data also indicates that a smaller number of respondents (7 or 11.29%) have earned a Doctorate degree. This highlights a strong commitment to professional growth among the respondents, with many actively pursuing advanced degrees to enhance their knowledge and skills. Their pursuit of postgraduate studies suggests a willingness to embrace the K12 program and a belief in the importance of

continuous learning.

Teaching Position or Plantilla Item

Teaching position refers to the present position or plantilla item the public senior high school hold as reflected in Table 5.

Table 5. *Plantilla Position*

<i>Plantilla Position</i>	<i>Administrator</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Assistant Principal II	1	16.7	0	0
Principal II	1	16.7	0	0
Principal I	1	16.7	0	0
Master Teacher I	0	0	1	1.6
SST I	0	0	7	11.3
Teacher I	0	0	5	8.1
Teacher II	0	0	34	54.8
Teacher III	3	50	15	24.2
Total	6	100	62	100

Table 5 reveals the distribution of plantilla positions among both administrator and teacher respondents. Among administrators, 50% hold the Teacher III position (Salary Grade 13), while 16.7% hold positions such as Assistant Principal 2, Principal I, and Principal 2. This data highlights the competitive nature of promotions within the agency, as advancement is based on performance and merit as outlined in the DECS Service Manual 2000. To enhance opportunities for career growth, schools should prioritize programs that equip teachers and administrators with the necessary skills and knowledge through training, seminars, and other job-related activities.

Among teachers, 11.3% hold the Special Science Teacher 1 (SST 1) position (Salary Grade 13), the same as those with Teacher 3 positions. Special Science teachers benefit from government scholarships under the Fast-tracked Scholarship Act of 2013, granting special privileges to Science and Mathematics graduates. This includes the ability to teach in their preferred schools even while awaiting licensure exam results and a starting salary higher than Teacher 1 entrants.

The majority of teacher respondents (58.4%) hold the Teacher II position (Salary Grade 12), with a smaller percentage (1.6%) holding the Master Teacher I position (Salary Grade 18). This disparity in the ratio of teachers to master teachers falls short of the 10:1 standard outlined in DepEd Order 70, s. 1998. This imbalance may limit the availability of technical assistance from master teachers, particularly in smaller schools.

Years in Service

Table 6. *Years in Service*

<i>Plantilla Position</i>	<i>Administrator</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
More than 10 years	5	83.3	22	35.48
4 – 10 years	1	16.7	17	27.42
0 – 3 years	0	0	23	37.1
Total	6	100	62	100

Table 6 reveals that a significant majority (83.3%) of administrator respondents have over 10 years of experience in service, while 16.7% have 4-10 years of experience. In contrast, a larger proportion of teacher respondents are relatively new to the profession.

This suggests that while experienced administrators may bring a wealth of knowledge and expertise to their roles, younger teachers may exhibit a greater willingness to embrace new approaches and adapt to changing demands. Research by Dörrenbächer et.al. (2019) supports this notion, citing the concept of Broadmann's Area 10, which suggests that younger adults possess a greater capacity for multitasking and attention switching. This could translate to a higher level of adaptability and flexibility among newer teachers, particularly in the context of modular instruction.

However, it's important to avoid generalizations and recognize that individual experiences and capabilities vary widely regardless of age or years of experience. Schools should provide ongoing professional development opportunities for all educators to enhance their skills and adapt to evolving teaching methodologies.

Performance Rating

Performance rating is the grade obtained by the public secondary teachers after having been evaluated based on access, quality, and governance. They were assessed annually through Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). The result can be Outstanding (O), Very Satisfactory (VS), Satisfactory (S), Unsatisfactory (US), and Poor (P). Teacher respondents' score for S.Y. 2020-2021. Table 7 shows the data.

Table 7 reveals that 100% of the respondents received a "Very Satisfactory" performance rating, indicating a high level of performance among both administrators and teachers in the selected senior high schools of Consolacion Districts 1 and 2. This positive performance

aligns with the criteria outlined in Department of Education Order No. 2 Series of 2015, which evaluates performance across three key areas: access, quality and relevance, and governance. The consistently high performance rating suggests a strong commitment to these areas, likely contributing to the respondents' effectiveness in implementing modular instruction. This data highlights the dedication and competence of educators in these schools, setting a positive foundation for the successful implementation of modular teaching strategies.

Table 7. Performance Rating

Performance Rating	Administrators		Teachers	
	f	%	f	%
Very satisfactory	6	100	62	100
Total	6	100	62	100

Level of Manifestation of Preparedness of the Respondent Groups in Modular Approach

This section presents the results of the Levels of Manifestation of Preparedness of the Respondent Groups in Modular Approach. The result from the analysis is presented as shown below:

Table 8. Preparedness

Statements	Teacher-Respondents			Administrator-Respondents		
	Mean	Sd	Verbal Description	Mean	Sd	Verbal Description
1. Planning and competence in teaching under the module-based instruction.	4.31	0.78	Very High	4.33	0.52	Very High
2. Integrating contextualized activities according to given competencies and special needs of learners.	4.16	0.75	High	4.17	0.75	High
3. Providing other supplementary learning resources to improve the instruction.	4.11	0.75	High	4.17	0.75	High
4. Attending online trainings and webinars to enhance my pedagogical knowledge and technical skills on module-based instruction.	4.24	0.74	Very High	4.50	0.84	Very High
5. Distributing to the learners promptly the modules to be used in the instruction and retrieving the accomplished modules based on the scheduled time and date.	4.53	0.74	High	4.67	0.52	Very High
6. Upskilling capabilities to teach under the module-based instruction.	4.13	0.78	High	4.33	0.52	Very High
7. Possessing master copies of modules ready for reproduction, reproducing modules enough for the learners and meeting sufficiency of reproduction materials.	4.39	0.82	Very High	4.50	0.55	Very High
8. Tapping LGUs, school and other sources for prompt and continued distribution of modules to the learners.	3.79	1.01	High	4.83	0.41	Very High
9. Producing worksheets or activity sheets, to supplement the module.	4.40	0.76	Very High	4.33	0.52	Very High
10. Preparing supplementary modules for struggling learners and providing additional modules for fast learners.	4.06	0.87	High	4.17	0.75	High
Aggregate Mean	4.21		Very High	4.40		Very High

Based on the level of manifestation of preparedness of the respondent groups in a modular approach, the teacher-respondents proved that they manifested very highly their preparedness in terms of distributing to the learners promptly the modules to be used in the instruction and retrieving the accomplished modules based on the scheduled time and date (4.53); producing worksheets or activity sheets, to supplement the module (4.4); and planning and competence in the teaching under the module-based instruction (4.31).

These findings imply that the selected senior high teachers in the district of Consolacion manifested preparedness in the distribution of modules, production of worksheets, and plan in order to efficiently deliver the modular teaching-learning to the target senior high school students in the district.

The teacher-respondents however, faired highly in terms of providing other supplementary learning resources to improve the instruction (4.11); tapping LGUs, school, and other sources for prompt and continued distribution of modules to the learners (3.79); and preparing supplementary modules for struggling learners and providing additional modules for fast learners (4.06).

It implies that there is a need for improvement among the teachers in their preparedness to provide supplementary learning materials, partner with local offices, and provision of supplementary modules to struggling senior high students and additional modules to fast senior high students in the selected schools in Consolacion District.

Among the administrators-respondents, they manifested preparedness with very high ratings in tapping LGUs, school, and other sources for prompt and continued distribution of modules to the learners (4.83); distributing to the learners promptly the modules to be used in the instruction and retrieving the accomplished modules based on the scheduled time and date (4.53); possessing master copies of

modules ready for reproduction, reproducing modules enough for the learners and meeting sufficiency of reproduction materials (4.5); and attending online training and webinars to enhance my pedagogical knowledge and technical skills on module-based instruction (4.24).

The senior high school administrators manifested preparedness in the module-based instruction by closely collaborating with Local Government Officials, prompt distribution of modules, possession of master copies for reproduction, and active participation in online training and webinars in the Consolacion District.

The administrators, however, have a high level of preparedness in Integrating contextualized activities according to given competencies and special needs of learners (4.17); providing other supplementary learning resources to improve the instruction and preparing supplementary modules for struggling learners (4.17); and providing additional modules for fast learners(4.17).

These findings proved that the administrators in Consolacion District should respond and develop an intervention to address the need for integration of contextualized tasks, provision of supplementary learning materials, and provision of additional modules to fast senior high learners.

In the study of Kariuki, Njoka, and Mbugua (2019), it was found out that teacher preparedness as indicated by preparation of lesson plans had an influence on pupils' performance in Mathematics in lower primary school. Preparation of schemes of work had no influence on performance. There were statistically significant differences between pupils' mean scores for schools where teachers prepared lesson plans and those who didn't. However, the study established that there was no statistically significant difference in the pupils' performance in relation to teachers' preparation of schemes of work.

As to the modular learning approach, Zamir (2019) concluded that modular teaching is more effective in the teaching learning process as compared to ordinary teaching methods. Because in this modular approach the students learn at their own pace. Further, the study also revealed that it is a free self-learning style in which immediate reinforcement, feedback is provided to practice exercise, which motivates the students and creates interest in them. Finally, the authors generalized that the modular approach helps to maximize the chances of student participation in the classroom in respect to fulfilling the given tasks at the spot. So the students feel free to learn in their own learning.

Level of Manifestation of Commitment of the Respondent Groups in Modular Approach

This section presents the results of the Level of Manifestation of Commitment of the Respondent Groups in Modular Approach. The results are presented and shown below:

Table 9. *Commitment*

Statements	Teacher-Respondents			Administrator-Respondents		
	Mean	sd	Verbal Description	Mean	sd	Verbal Description
Reaching out learners through online means to provide explanation and renew interest as well as provide needed intervention to facilitate understanding.	4.39	0.75	Very High	4.67	0.52	Very High
Attending related or relevant trainings/webinars that would provide professional development.	4.23	0.78	Very High	4.33	0.82	Very High
Organizing the colleagues to establish support system among teachers using personal resources in the preparation of modules for struggling learners.	4.16	0.71	High	4.17	0.41	High
Using personal resources in the preparation of modules for struggling learners.	4.26	0.83	Very High	3.33	1.03	Medium
Providing template or worksheet to learners to help them work the activities at the teacher's personal expense.	4.10	0.80	High	3.83	0.98	High
Demonstrating adjustment and flexibility for learners in difficult circumstances and conducting coaching sessions.	4.10	0.86	High	4.33	0.82	Very High
Collaborating with co-teachers to do the printing and binding of the modules and special interventions activities.	4.53	0.62	Very High	4.50	0.55	Very High

Taking the initiative to fund the printing of modules for the mass reproduction using personal resources to meet the necessary quantity of modules.	3.71	1.21	High	3.83	0.75	High
Tapping support from stakeholders to address inadequacies of materials.	3.42	1.22	High	4.83 ¹	0.41	Very High
Preparing localized modules for supplementary learning materials to reinforce learning.	4.26	0.97	Very High	4.17	0.75	High
Aggregate Mean	4.11		High	4.20		High

Table 9 presents the level of manifestation of the commitment of the respondent groups in a modular approach. Based on the data presented, the teacher-respondents fare very highly in collaborating with co-teachers to do the printing and binding of the modules and special interventions activities (4.53); reaching out to learners through online means to provide explanation and renew interest as well as provide needed intervention to facilitate understanding (4.39); Using personal resources in the preparation of modules for struggling learners (4.26), and preparing localized modules for supplementary learning materials to reinforce learning (4.26).

The teacher respondents in this study showed very high commitment in collaboration with fellow teachers, reaching out to learners, utilization of personal resources, and preparation of localized modules for the senior high school students in the selected schools in Consolacion District.

Among the indicators with the lowest weighted means are the teacher's commitment to providing templates or worksheets to learners to help them work the activities at the teacher's personal expense (4.10); demonstrating adjustment and flexibility for learners in difficult circumstances and conducting coaching sessions (4.10); taking the initiative to fund the printing of modules for the mass reproduction using personal resources to meet the necessary quantity of modules (3.71); tapping support from stakeholders to address inadequacies of materials (3.42).

Based on the preceding data, there is a need for training and intervention in order to improve the teachers' commitment in the provision of the worksheet to learners, flexibility in difficult situations, an initiative to raise funds to purchase printing materials, and partnership with stakeholders regarding the needs for implementation of modular learning approach for senior high school in Consolacion District.

On the other hand, the administrator-respondents manifested their commitment very highly in Tapping support from stakeholders to address inadequacies of materials (4.83); Reaching out to learners through online means to provide explanation and renew interest as well as provide needed intervention to facilitate understanding (4.67); collaborating with co-teachers to do the printing and binding of the modules and special interventions activities (4.5).

The senior high school administration in the selected schools in Consolacion District have proven their commitment in involving stakeholders to address the needs for module production, helping learners to keep on track of their online learning, and strengthening collaboration among senior high school teachers.

The administrators, however, have a high level of manifestation of commitment in using personal resources in the preparation of modules for struggling learners (3.33); Providing templates or worksheets to learners to help them work the activities at the teacher's personal expense (3.83); and taking the initiative to fund the printing of modules for the mass reproduction using personal resources to meet the necessary quantity of modules (3.83).

The above findings proved that the administrators' commitment to the delivery of modular learning needs to be improved in the areas of the personal fund, utilization for struggling learners, provision of the worksheet to learners, an initiative for fundraising for module production to insure the uninterrupted learning flow among senior high school students in Consolacion District.

Czarnecki (2020) referred to teacher commitment as "grace under fire" @. 3 1). He linked the professional commitment of teachers to student needs. In response to the question, "An 'extra' curricular commitment: How much can teachers give?," Czarnecki (2020) implied that teachers will give almost everything they can to the meaningful pursuit of growth and success for their students.

Hatch (2021) spoke of rediscovering hope, the greatest teaching strategy. He lamented how the element of hope has been lost from the classroom and suggested that schools can become, with teacher commitment, the one place in which students in a throw-away society can succeed.

With the strength of professional commitment that the researcher found in the present study, often in the midst of undesirable circumstances, there is hope. A key element will be the ability of the guardians of the educational enterprise to provide the resources and the climate for this hope to be filled.

Level of Manifestation of Resiliency of the Respondent Groups in Modular Approach

This section presents the results of the Level of Manifestation of Resiliency of the Respondent Groups in Modular Approach. The results are presented and shown below:

Table 10. *Resiliency*

Statements	Teacher-Respondents			Administrator-Respondents		
	Mean	sd	Verbal Description	Mean	sd	Verbal Description
Initiating to learn in providing modular instruction.	4.47	0.67	Very High	4.50	0.55	Very High
Planning lesson delivery in the absence of webinars conducted during the new normal.	4.37	0.63	Very High	4.50	0.55	Very High
Integrating contextualized lessons as a supplemental module as a personal initiative and doing the prescribed tasks for modular instruction without waiting for the concrete instruction from administrator to prevent delay.	4.29	0.61	Very High	4.17	0.41	High
Providing other supplementary learning resources based on own initiative due to shortage of supplies and materials.	4.29	0.71	Very High	4.00	0.63	High
Engaging in activities such as training, webinars and physical exercises and group dynamics to maintain mental health and well-being.	4.11	0.55	High	4.33	0.52	Very High
Possessing training materials on personal initiative related to module-based instruction as ready reference.	4.02	0.76	High	4.33	0.52	Very High
Self-learning on pedagogical instruction using modules without waiting for the training provision from DepED officials.	4.29	0.61	Very High	4.17	0.41	High
Brainstorming and sharing with colleagues on best practices in responding to problematic situations with parents and in dealing positively with delinquent student.	4.34	0.63	Very High	4.50	0.55	Very High
Demonstrating initiative in overcoming insufficiency of printing materials and equipment as well as tapping LGUs for provision of reproduction equipment to address delay in the production.	4.05	0.66	High	4.33	0.52	Very High
Reaching agreeable compromise/actions with colleagues regarding parent and learner problematic situations.	4.31	0.76	Very High	4.50	0.55	Very High
Aggregate Mean	4.25		Very High	4.33		Very High

Table 11 presents the level of manifestation of the resiliency of the respondent groups in a modular approach. The teacher-respondents manifested their resiliency very highly in initiating to learn in providing modular instruction (4.47); planning lesson delivery in the absence of webinars conducted during the new normal (4.37); brainstorming and sharing with colleagues on best practices in responding to problematic situations with parents and in dealing positively with the delinquent student (4.34).

The teachers, as shown in the above findings manifested resiliency in the provision of modular instruction, lesson planning, brainstorming, and sharing of best practices even in the midst of a pandemic when there is risk and limited mobility.

The teachers, however, fared highly in their manifestation of resiliency in engaging in activities such as training, webinars and physical exercises and group dynamics to maintain mental health and well-being (4.11); possessing training materials on a personal initiative related to module-based instruction as ready reference (4.02); and demonstrating initiative in overcoming insufficiency of printing materials and equipment as well as tapping LGUs for provision of reproduction equipment to address delay in the production (4.05).

The teachers handling senior high students in the Consolacion district need to attend online training and webinars, possess module-based reference materials, and overcome the insufficiency of printing materials. This will further improve their resiliency in facing the challenges of modular instruction across learning areas.

For the administrator-respondents, they manifested their resiliency very highly in brainstorming and sharing with colleagues on best practices in responding to problematic situations with parents and in dealing positively with the delinquent student (4.5); Initiating to learn in providing modular instruction (4.5); Planning lesson delivery in the absence of webinars conducted during the new normal

(4.5); Reaching agreeable compromise/actions with colleagues regarding parent and learner problematic situations (4.5).

The senior high school administrators in the Consolacion district showed resiliency in brainstorming, provision of modular instruction, lesson planning, and the practice of compromise between and among teachers and parents.

On the other hand, the administrators have a high level of manifestation of resiliency in integrating contextualized lessons as a supplemental module as a personal initiative and doing the prescribed tasks for modular instruction without waiting for the concrete instruction from the administrator to prevent delay (4.17); providing other supplementary learning resources based on own initiative due to shortage of supplies and materials (4.0); and self-learning on pedagogical instruction using modules without waiting for the training provision from DepED officials (4.17).

The senior high school administrators in the Consolacion district need to address their deficiencies in their resiliency specifically in contextualizing lessons, provision of supplementary learning materials, and utilization of modules as the main tool for self-learning and pedagogical instruction across learning areas. These weaknesses may be addressed through conferences, orientation and sharing of best practices among teachers in the Consolacion District.

The study of Ellison et al., (2019) set out to understand what enables teachers to develop and sustain resilience and what lessons there are for the school organization. Drawing on the experiences of an inner-city school, in a socioeconomically disadvantaged area, the life of one school can point to the realities of developing and sustaining resilience in teachers' lives. There is no universally accepted definition of resilience, and in reviewing the literature it was established that it was an unstable construct that involved psychological, behavioral, and cognitive functioning in many settings. These settings include the personal, the professional, and the organizational.

Sisto et al., (2019) found when reviewing five decades of research on resilience that the phenomenon was influenced by individual circumstances, situations, and environments. This study did not concentrate on individuals' strengths but focused on teachers' lives, including experiences from home that impacted school life. The questionnaire mapped the territory for investigation and provided the basis for the interviews, and the recalling of a critical incident allowed for deeper recollection of teachers' lives. Teachers' recollection of their teaching careers helped to explore experiences and strategies they employed to sustain them on their journey and provided insights on how they developed resilience.

Table 11. Summary of Table for the level of manifestation on modular approach

	Teachers		Administrators	
	Aggregate Mean	Verbal Description	Aggregate Mean	Verbal Description
Preparedness	4.21	Very High	4.40	Very High
Commitment	4.11	High	4.20	High
Resiliency	4.25	Very High	4.33	Very High

Based on the teachers' perceptions, they have very high levels of preparedness (4.21) and resiliency (4.35) in implementing the modular learning approach while high in their level of commitment.

For the administrators, they too have high levels of preparedness (4.40) and resiliency (4.33) in the implementation of the modular learning approach while high in their level of commitment.

There is a similarity in the characteristics of the teachers and administrators. Both groups of respondents need to increase their level of commitment. This finding can be attributed to the teacher's and administrators' attitude towards modular learning delivery because for them it is more tedious and more demanding of their time and effort. The distribution is another challenging task as there are parents who do not follow a schedule of distribution.

The study of Brooks (2019), on the resiliency among secondary teachers serving at-risk populations: a phenomenological study, examined lived experiences, perceptions, and behaviors of resilient secondary teachers working with at-risk populations in contrast to burned-out teachers. The study utilized a qualitative design with a descriptive approach and phenomenological methodology. This study addressed the following question: What are the shared experiences of secondary teachers working with at-risk populations who are resilient to workplace stressors and teacher burnout within their role as educators? The variables were behaviors and actions regarding resiliency to workplace stressors and teacher burnout and social interactions regarding resiliency to workplace stressors and teacher burnout. Teacher resiliency was defined as "a quality that enables teachers to maintain their commitment to teaching and their teaching practices despite challenging conditions and recurring setbacks" (Kutsyuruba et al., 2019). Teacher burnout was defined as a disorder characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and diminished individual achievement.

Results from the data collected yielded the following: Resilient teachers rely on peers for support. Resilient teachers maintain work/life balance. Resilient teachers are creative and flexible. Resilient teachers perceive a disconnect between their job and the role of administrators. Resilient teachers perceive most administrators as unsupportive or absent. Resilient teachers integrate technology to make their jobs easier and appeal to 21st-century students.

Building teacher resiliency and thereby limiting teacher burnout will continue to be an important issue for state and local educational agencies. Widening national teacher shortages and periodic teachers' strikes such as those in 2018 in West Virginia, Kentucky,

Oklahoma, and Arizona is a testament to the stressful situations and poor working conditions in which many teachers find themselves. Although teacher resiliency cannot put food on the table or buy classroom textbooks, teacher resiliency can provide educators with a renewed passion for teaching, camaraderie, and valuable coping mechanisms.

Relationship Between School Administrators' and Level of Preparedness and Commitment

This section presents the results of the Relationship Between School Administrators' and Level of Preparedness and Commitment. The results are presented and shown below:

Table 12. *Relationship Between School Administrators And Level Of Preparedness And Commitment*

<i>Administrators vs Teachers perception</i>	<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	<i>P-Value</i>
Preparedness	0.380	0.457
Commitment	-0.380	0.458

The test of the relationship between the levels of perception of administrators' preparedness and teachers' preparedness in the modular learning approach has a Pearson r-value of 0.380 and a p-value of 0.457 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the administrators' level of preparedness and teachers' level of preparedness in the modular learning approach.

Moreover, the test of the relationship between the levels of perception of administrators' commitment and teachers' commitment in the modular learning approach has a Pearson r value of -0.380 and a p-value of 0.458 which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the administrators' level of commitment and teachers' level of commitment in the modular learning approach.

The above finding proved that the administrators' degree of preparation is not a determinant or predictor of teachers' preparation. The same is also true in their commitment.

Due to the nature of tasks and magnitude of responsibilities of the administrators in the implementation of the modular learning approach, their level of preparedness and commitment do not follow the teachers. Teachers are front liners of the modular learning have specific tasks like production or printing, sorting and stapling the modules according to the learning areas assigned to them and according to the number of students and grade levels.

According to a teacher respondent "The teachers find it more challenging to implement modular learning because this is new to us. Although we are not assured of the quality of learning we appeal to parents to assist, to guide and to motivate their children to do independent learning as modules are learner-friendly and easy to comprehend".

Another teacher explained that "We are prepared but since this instructional delivery is new we cannot anticipate what will be the challenges along the way. Our commitment to quality education amidst this pandemic is tested and validated".

The preparedness and commitment of the administrators and teachers in the implementation of the modular learning approach are independent of each other. Some school personnel may comply with the required preparations but not necessarily are committed to this new delivery mode.

Al-Mahdy et al., (2018) study, revealed that principals who adopt a transformational instructional leadership approach that is distributed, collaborative, and shared are better able to influence their teachers' commitment, professional involvement, and innovation. Notwithstanding the differences and similarities in leadership characters, it would appear that the teachers in the study schools have high regard for and acceptance of their principals' leadership behaviors. Overall, the findings in this study reveal that the teachers perceive their principals as inclusive, open to different ideas, and appreciative of their hard work. These perceptions illuminate the ripple effect of good school governance as the principals' leadership behaviors have been shown to have an indirect and direct influence on students' academic performance and participation in extra-curricular activities. Principals and teachers articulated the following understanding of leadership and the specific leadership behaviors that have significance for teachers' commitment, professional involvement, and innovation. Three major themes emerged from the data findings – Leadership and Values, Leadership and Student Focus, and Leadership: Policies and Evaluation. Each theme has specific sub-themes that are relevant to the research purpose and questions.

Relationship Between Teacher's Level of Preparedness and Their Extent of Resiliency

This section presents the results of relationship between teacher's level of preparedness and their extent of resiliency of the respondent groups. The results are presented and shown below:

The test of the relationship between the level of preparedness of the teachers and the extent of their resilience in the implementation of modular learning in basic education yields an R-value of 0.658 and a p-value of 0.000 which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the teachers' level of preparedness and their extent of resilience when implementing the modular approach in teaching-learning.

Table 13. *Relationship Between Teacher's Level of Preparedness and Their Extent of Resiliency*

	Pearson Correlation	P-Value
Preparedness vs Resiliency	0.658	0.000

The test of the relationship between the level of preparedness of the teachers and the extent of their resilience in the implementation of modular learning in basic education yields an R-value of 0.658 and a p-value of 0.000 which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the teachers' level of preparedness and their extent of resilience when implementing the modular approach in teaching-learning.

This implies that if the teachers are prepared they become more resilient. The availability of the modules for reproduction and printing materials are factors of their preparedness not to mention the time and their technical expertise. According to one teacher respondent "Modules are prepared weeks before the distribution this allows more time for teachers to adjust should there be glitches in the printing and shortage of printing materials". Indeed the teachers manifest resilience because they are set to meet their targets to distribute the modules despite the many challenges.

Teachers' resilience is measured by their capacity to stick to their tasks and in the achievement of their goals despite the problems and challenges they encounter.

In the study of Chen et al., (2019), the first stand-out is the linkage of the leadership practice of modeling the way with six of the seven dimensions of resilience. Flexible: thoughts were not correlated with any of the leadership practices. In personal experience and observations of other professional principals, the researcher has found this to be an essential truth in practice. The most successful school leaders are those who model the expectations that they have for staff members. To achieve a high level of commitment to education, the principal must model that for their staff whether it is their commitment to personal continuing education or the adaptation and application of new technologies. Those leaders who model change in their behavior are those who achieve the smoothest transitions in educational settings.

The next most frequent occurrence of a positive correlation is that of inspiring a shared vision. High-achieving schools are those led by principals who articulate their values and vision to their co-workers. School settings are unique in the physical construct of the workplace, classroom teachers working with students are not so easily observed unobtrusively. Therefore, teachers have a lot of autonomy for their function in the classroom. The principal leader influences how teachers make decisions from a remote place, that of faculty meetings, individual conferences, and informal meetings. These are the places that principals communicate to staff their expectations for the overall tone of the school. When those messages are clear and receive a significant commitment from school staff, the school can respond with greater resilience to the demands and constraints of public school education.

Challenging the process was positively correlated with four of the dimensions of resilience. Principals who challenge the process are those who can integrate facilitate change in their schools by helping to tailor the demands to the culture of their school. Principals who can assess the strengths and weaknesses of the new challenge, select personnel who can easily embrace the new strategies, provide resources to support the change, and support the change process through sustained staff development are more effective leaders. In challenging the process, successful principals adapt external demands to fit the personnel and culture of the school.

The dimension of resilience that did not correlate with any of the leadership practices also was interesting in its absence. Flexible, thoughts had no correlations, positive or negative, with any of the leadership practices. Since this was a survey of school leaders, the researcher expected to find some correlation with thought and thinking processes.

Challenges and Barriers Encountered by the Teachers in Modular Approach

This section presents the results of Challenges and Barriers Encountered by the Teachers in Modular Approach. The results are presented and shown below:

Table 14. *Challenges and barriers encountered by the teachers in modular approach*

Challenges and barriers to modular instructions	Rank	
	Teachers' Respondents	Administrators' Respondents
Lack of support from home tutors	5	5
Prompt returns and distribution of modules	4	4
Lack of available printing equipment/materials	2	1.5
Unanswered/activities	3	3
Selective compliance/duplication of answer keys	1	1.5

As shown in table 14, the most challenging and barrier in modular instruction for teachers' respondents is the selective compliance/duplication of answer keys, followed by lack of available printing equipment/materials, The relevance of modules in

schools is of utmost priority especially in the implementation of the K-12 program during the pandemic. This problem is not unique in Consolacion. This is prevalent in other districts and schools which are isolated.

While the least challenging for teachers is the lack of support from home tutors. For administrators' respondents, the most challenging are the selective compliance/duplication of answer keys and lack of available printing equipment/materials, followed by unanswered activities, while the least challenging for administrators is the lack of support of teachers. It means that both teachers and administrators were challenged the most with the selective compliance/duplication of answer keys, while they were least challenged with the lack of support from home tutors.

In the study of Dangle and Somaoang (2020), the great number of activities in each module is one of the main problems that emerged in the implementation of Modular Distance Learning. The Department of Education should consider this problem, reduce the activities, and take out the unnecessary topics so that mastery will be attained as much as possible. As some of the parents said, the lesser the better. One of the concerns of the students is that they do not have enough time to answer all the modules within a week.

Therefore, if DepEd cannot extend the duration of accomplishing the modules, they must lessen the activities. We all know that mistakes cannot be avoided at times. Thus, teachers should re-evaluate the modules, and they must make sure that all the lessons or activities are appropriate to the needs of the learners. The parents, as well as the students, are right; the instructions in every exercise must be clear enough for the learners to understand. The topics must be simplified, and teachers must give more examples.

Moreover, all printed images in the learning modules should be of high quality. Given that COVID-19 cases in the Philippines remain significant, face-to-face learning is still not feasible in most areas. However, the researcher suggests that blended learning could be a viable option in regions with low or no active cases, such as rural schools like BNHS. For urban areas like BCNHS, where most students have internet access, online learning could be implemented. For students unable to access the internet, special accommodations, such as home visits, could be considered. Besides traditional communication like calls and texts, social media—particularly Messenger—is one of the most widely used channels between teachers, parents, and students. Therefore, teachers are encouraged to be accessible online and to promptly address parents' and students' concerns with patience and responsiveness.

To support the Philippine educational system during the pandemic, collaboration between the Department of Education and the government is essential. Schools should be provided with adequate resources and funding. The Department of Education should grant teachers greater autonomy in developing modules, while ensuring that these materials undergo quality validation and monitoring to track progress effectively.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study findings revealed various aspects of the respondents' profiles, perceptions, and challenges related to the implementation of the modular learning approach in selected senior high schools. The profile analysis showed that the majority of respondents are in their prime years, with a significant number holding Masters' degrees or having completed academic requirements for the program. Furthermore, the distribution of positions among the respondent groups indicates challenges in promotion within the agency, emphasizing the importance of enhancing skills through training and seminars.

Regarding preparedness and commitment, both administrators and teachers demonstrated high levels of readiness and resilience in implementing the modular learning approach, alongside a strong commitment to the process. The respondent teachers and administrators in the selected senior high schools in Consolacion District 1 and 2, Cebu Province have very satisfactory performance. Both groups of respondents have a very high level of manifestation of preparedness, commitment, and resiliency in the delivery of the modular instruction in the Senior High School hence the administrators and teachers achieved in delivering successfully the modular learning approach. While there was no significant relationship found between administrators' and teachers' preparedness levels, a notable correlation was identified between teachers' preparedness and their resilience during the implementation of the modular approach.

Additionally, the study highlighted the top challenges and barriers encountered by teachers in modular instruction, with selective compliance/duplication of answer keys and the lack of printing equipment/materials being the most prevalent issues. Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensure the smooth execution of the modular approach in teaching-learning environments. Overall, the study underscores the importance of ongoing support and professional development initiatives to equip educators with the necessary skills and resources for successful modular instruction implementation.

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